

Exploring organizational management of extrovert school leadership

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed at determining the personality traits of extroversion and introversion of school leadership and evaluating their organizational management in Federal Government Educational Institutions (FGEIs). A quantitative research design along with a positivist paradigm was followed. The total population consisted of 68 school principals and 592 teachers of FGEIs in the Gujranwala, Fazaia, and Lahore Regions from which 54 principals and 381 teachers were selected using a random sampling technique. Eysenck Personality Inventory (EPI) was deployed to collect information about personality traits and data regarding organizational management, the researchers used a self-developed questionnaire. Pearson correlation r and t -tests were deployed for inferential stats. The results showed that extrovert school leaders perform their duties well as they hold a clear concept of the vision and mission of the organization, set up an accepted procedure to plan short-term and long-term goals, share responsibilities with all stakeholders following their skills, and ensure the smooth functioning of the school with the help of all stakeholders. In comparison, introverted school principals show less interest in the organizational management of their schools. Moreover, organizational management of school leadership has a positive correlation with the personality trait of extroversion and a significant difference can be seen in organizational management of an extrovert and an introvert school principal. It was recommended that the performance indicators and standards of school principals should be effectively communicated to school leadership. Introvert school leadership should be provided with the necessary psychological training to reduce this shortcoming of personality.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The school principal plays a significant role in achieving organizational objectives. School principal holds the responsibility of supporting and assisting the school faculty. The principal works as a team leader and provides directions and coordination to the whole team of an educational institution. School principal focuses upon the better quality of the teaching-learning process and maintains high standards of teaching for the education of students within a school. The principal plays the role of supervisor and facilitator for the faculty members. He keeps up-to-date knowledge of modern educational concepts and teaching techniques and provides guidelines to the faculty and the students accordingly. In this way, the principal plays a vital role in quality teaching, policy implementation, better command and control, and guidance and evaluation for

both the faculty and the students. He discusses discipline issues with the faculty members and provides them guidance on how to resolve such issues. He focuses upon the overall academic and non-academic improvement of the educational institution [1]–[3]. The principal should hold a close and healthy relationship with the parents and guardians of the students. He maintains an updated record of students' academic achievements. He focuses upon the overall personality development of students and holds continuous contact with the parents. In this way, he performs his duties in close association with the other stakeholders. He provides the necessary materials and instructions so that they may be able to complete the task of cleanliness of the school [4].

The principal has to keep in contact with different departments, organizations police, other law enforcement agencies, also health and disaster management authority. He has to talk to the media in different situations related to academic and other activities of the institution. To cope with all this, the principal should have excellent written and oral communication skills. The principal submits reports upon the achievements of the students and the overall progress of the institution to the higher authorities [5], [6]. The principal focuses on the organizational management of the institution and involves all the stakeholders. To achieve the goal of better organizational management he holds an unambiguous conception of the vision and mission of the organization, fully comprehends/applies all necessary rules and policies of the organization [7].

In this study, the researchers explored the organizational management of extrovert school principals. The study was conducted in Federal Government Educational Institutions (FGEIs). These institutions are working throughout Pakistan and focus upon providing education, which is based on quality and innovation, to its students [8]. Mostly the students in these schools are the wards of serving or retired army persons and the civilian residents of cantonments. FGEIs aims to groom the students to become useful citizens of Pakistan [9]. The organizational management of extroverted school principals plays a vital role in achieving the aims of FGEIs. This study would help the school leadership in FGEIs improve their performance through maintaining better organizational management.

Personality traits are such capabilities of an individual that are explicitly related to him or her only. These are commonly exhibited through the behavior, personality, and feeling of an individual. Eysenck categorized the personality traits by using the method of factor analysis. Initially, Eysenck has based on a supposition that personality has two super traits. He categorized that human personality as either extrovert/introvert or emotionally stable/neurotic. He further assumed that extrovert people are friendly and highly receptive while introvert people are calm and less enthusiastic. There are different methods used to measure personality. Eysenck presented a technique to calculate the super traits of extroversion/introversion and emotional stability/neuroticism. This technique is known as Eysenck's personality inventory (EPI). It contains a simple Yes-No format to reply to the items to identify extroversion/introversion scores of an individual [10]. The EPI Performa provides the following types of scores: i) The lie score: It tells about the extent to which the respondent has tried to show himself/herself good. It ranges from 0 to 9; ii) The E score: This score tells us about the extroversion/introversion of the respondent. Its values vary from 0 to 24. The following Table 1 shows major characteristics of personality traits of extroversion and introversion.

Table 1. Key characteristics of extrovert and introvert individuals

Sr No	Personality trait	Key characteristics
01	Extroversion	Lively, hopeful, stable, consistent, energetic
02	Introversion	Unstable, gloomy, inflexible, reserved, quick-tempered

Simply saying performance is such a procedure which is adopted on the instructions of some senior official. It helps for the betterment of the organization and other stakeholders. It consists of all such activities which play an active role in achieving the organizational objectives [11], [12].

It is such a method in which the ability and competency of an individual or organization are calculated. It tells us about the working of an organization and the achievement of organizational objectives. It is a well-defined and permanent process in which the output of an individual or organization is assessed. The performance measurement provides a basis to identify issues and challenges which create a hurdle in achieving the targets. Moreover, it helps in future planning for the performance improvement of an organization [13], [14].

These are such specific skilled duties which a principal is expected to perform on regular basis. These standards help us in data collection regarding the performance of school principals. The major focus of these standards is upon enthusiasm, vision, adjustability, and adaptability of school principals. These help the principals to improve their performance [15]–[17]. Virginia Department of Education, Virginia has stated seven such standards which are helpful to explore and improve the performance of schools [18].

In the following paragraphs these standards have been stated shortly: i) Provision of coaching and guidance to all stakeholders. The school principal facilitates the students to achieve academic progress. He follows a shared vision of leadership for the improvement of the school. He provides professional coaching and guidance to all the concerned including faculty, students, parents, and others; ii) Managing school environment. A positive, safe, and learning-based environment of school help to achieve the academic success of students. The principal should promote a healthy environment in school. He is responsible to facilitate the students by providing them with a good learning environment to achieve their academic progress; iii) Faculty management. The faculty members play a significant role to achieve academic excellence and organizational objectives. The principal should focus upon the best utilization of the faculty members keeping their attitude, aptitude, and professional skills in view; iv) Managing official correspondence. Principal office receives certain policy letters which higher authorities desire to implement for the betterment of the school and students. Moreover, senior administration needs essential data regarding the faculty and the students for future planning. In this way, the role of the principal office is very important. The principal is responsible for the management of all correspondence; v) Human relationship management. The principal is the key person who has to interact with all stakeholders of the school. This is his duty to utilize capabilities and communication skills to create a good working relationship with all stakeholders. This may improve the overall environment of the school and result in the academic excellence of the students; vi) Developing professional skills. The principal should engage himself in the process of continuous professional development. He should focus on contributing to the profession. He should represent high professional standards. He focuses on professional ethics while interacting with all stakeholders; vii) Student learning expansion. Leadership behavior of school principals increases the academic progress of the students. So, he should focus to follow all the performance standards. This may ultimately result in the academic excellence of the learners.

The principal of an educational institution focuses on the organizational management of the institution. He uses all available resources to achieve a better level of organizational management. He involves all the stakeholders including faculty, students, parents, and other concerned public and private organizations [19]–[22]. In the following paragraph, some examples of the performance indicators are mentioned [23]–[25].

The principal holds a clear concept of the vision and mission of the organization and presents it to all concerned effectively. He understands all compulsory rules and regulations of the organization and employs all those, in true letter and spirit. He presents the vision, mission, and aims of the organization very clearly to all the concerned. He holds complete working knowledge of the laws of the organization and effectively communicates the laws of the organization. He ensures a safe, secure, efficient, and orderly supply of facilities. He efficiently monitors development in infrastructure on a priority basis. He sets up an accepted procedure to plan short-term and long-term goals and ensures effective allocation of resources to achieve such goals. He focuses on maintaining the financial records, plans, and effective school budget, and prepares it keeping the mission and vision of the organization in view. He ensures accountability for all funds and observes strict compliance with departmental rules in handling financial issues. He shares responsibilities with all stakeholders following their skills and ensures the smooth functioning of the school with the help of all stakeholders.

The study aimed at determining the personality traits of extroversion and introversion of school principals. The major objective of the study was to evaluate the organizational management of school principals in FGEIs. Following were research questions of the study: i) How are the school principals classified as extroverted/introverts based on their personality traits?; ii) Does there exist any relationship between extrovert school principals and their organizational management?; and iii) Does there exist any meaningful difference between the organizational management of extrovert and introvert school principals?

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was co-relational as it aimed to explore the correlation between extrovert school principals and their organizational management. Here the organizational management was taken as a criterion variable whereas the personality trait of extroversion was considered as a predictor variable. A quantitative research design along with a positivist paradigm was followed in this study. It helped the researchers to collect data from a selected sample of the population using questionnaires.

The total population consisted of 68 school principals and 592 teachers of FGEIs Gujranwala, Fazaia, and Lahore Regions. A random sampling technique was adopted to select the sample and it consisted of 54 school principals and 381 teachers. Table 2 shows the total population and selected sample.

Table 2. Population and sample of the study

Location	Total population				Selected sample			
	Male teachers	Female teachers	Male principals	Female principals	Male teachers	Female teachers	Male principals	Female principals
FGEIs Gujranwala	112	105	09	13	095	082	07	11
FGEIs Fazaia	092	083	12	10	045	041	09	08
FGEIs Lahore	108	092	08	16	060	058	05	14

There were two types of research questionnaires used in this study, first research questionnaires. EPI was deployed to collect information about the personality traits of the school principals [10]. It helped to identify the principals as extroverts or introverts. This questionnaire was filled in by the principals. To collect data regarding organizational management, the researchers used a self-developed questionnaire. It was prepared in the light of the most recent literature and was refined as per recommendations of the experts. It consisted of a total of 24 items and contained dimensions like working knowledge, financial management and budgeting, and involvement of stakeholders. A demographic information form was also included in the research instruments to collect information like gender, academic qualification, and work experience from the respondents. Second, pilot testing and reliability. Every effort was made to ensure content validity and internal consistency of items of the questionnaire. The research instrument was administered to 12 principals and 57 teachers as a pilot study. Overall internal reliability of the instrument was found to be 0.84.

Data collection was done by deploying the survey method. This method helped the researchers to collect primary data for the study. Demographic information form and the research instruments were sent to the principals and teachers of the selected FGEIs of Gujranwala, Fazaia, and Lahore regions through registered mail.

The collected data were analyzed for descriptive and inferential stats using SPSS version 24.0. Mean and standard deviation was calculated in descriptive stats based on which answer to the research question 1 was obtained. Pearson correlation r was deployed for the second research question, whereas an independent sample t -test was also deployed for the third question, using inferential stats.

3. RESULTS

For data analysis, SPSS version 24.0 was deployed. This program helped the researchers to calculate descriptive and inferential statistics. Percentages and related figures were obtained through descriptive statistics. To determine correlation and significant difference, inferential statistics were used. Pearson correlation r and t -test were deployed for this purpose.

Out of a total of 54 school principals, 21 were male while 33 were female. Similarly, there 200 were male while 181 female teachers out of a total of 381 school teachers. Figure 1 shows a graphical presentation of the gender of respondents of both the principals and the teachers. Out of a total of 54 school principals, 33 were having work experience between 1 to 5 years whereas 21 were having work experience of more than 5 years. Similarly, 245 teachers were having work experience between 1 to 5 years whereas 136 were having work experience of more than 5 years. Figure 2 shows a graphical presentation of the work experience of both the principals and the teachers.

The EPI was used to identify school principals as extroverts or introverts. It was found through analysis that there were 25 introvert and 29 extrovert principals out of a selected sample of 54 school principals. Table 3 showed their classification as extrovert and introvert.

Figure 1. Gender of respondents (principals and teachers)

Figure 2. Work experience (principals and teachers)

Table 3. Classification of school principals as extrovert and introvert

Sr No	Personality trait	Number of principals
01	Introvert	25
02	Extrovert	29

Table 4 shows a comparison of views of extrovert and introvert school principals on organizational management. It is evident that extrovert principals hold a clear concept of the vision and mission of the organization, present the vision and mission of the organization to all concerned effectively, understand all compulsory rules and regulations of the organization, employ all compulsory rules and regulations of the organization in true letter and spirit, hold complete working knowledge of the laws of the organization, effectively communicate the laws of the organization, ensure a safe, secure, efficient, and orderly supply of facilities, monitor development in infrastructure on a priority basis, recognize key issues in organizational, operational, or resource-related activities, timely resolve key issues in organizational, operational, or resource-related activities, remain consistent in solving key issues in organizational, operational, or resource-related activities, deal with key issues in an effective manner, set up an accepted procedure to plan short-term and long-term goals, ensure effective allocation of resources to achieve such goals, focus on maintaining the financial records, plan an effective school budget, prepare the school budget keeping the mission and vision of the organization in view, ensure accountability for all funds, ensure following the departmental rules in handling financial issues, follow policies to ensure school accountability, establish strategies to include all stakeholders in school projects, allow them to share in the process of management decisions, share responsibilities with all stakeholders following their skills, ensure the smooth functioning of the school with the help of all stakeholders with mean 3.48, 3.46, 3.28, 3.14, 3.38, 3.36, 3.18, 3.24, 3.27, 3.59, 3.34, 3.63, 3.47, 3.22, 3.16, 3.21, 3.44, 3.45, 3.49, 3.33, 3.39, 3.54, 3.81 and 3.89 respectively. The mean scores for introvert principals for the same items are as 1.84, 1.86, 1.88, 1.83, 1.94, 1.96, 1.86, 1.73, 1.95, 1.91, 1.92, 1.98, 1.68, 1.71, 1.93, 1.99, 1.81, 1.92, 1.98, 1.97, 1.53, 1.91, 1.85 and 1.49 respectively. This comparison indicates that the extrovert principals performed well in all activities of organizational management than introvert principals.

Table 4. Comparison of organizational management of extrovert and introvert principals

Sr No	Organizational management activity	Extrovert principals		Introvert principals	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
01	The principal holds a clear concept of the vision and mission of the organization.	3.48	0.53	1.84	0.82
02	He presents the vision and mission of the organization to all concerned effectively.	3.46	0.64	1.86	0.93
03	The principal understands all compulsory rules and regulations of the organization.	3.28	0.44	1.88	0.87
04	He employs all compulsory rules and regulations of the organization in true letter and spirit.	3.14	0.57	1.83	0.81
05	The principal holds complete working knowledge of the laws of the organization.	3.38	0.63	1.94	0.89
06	He effectively communicates the laws of the organization.	3.36	0.74	1.96	0.91
07	The principal ensures a safe, secure, efficient, and orderly supply of facilities.	3.18	0.64	1.86	0.84
08	He efficiently monitors development in infrastructure on a priority basis.	3.24	0.67	1.73	0.82
09	The principal recognizes key issues in organizational, operational, or resource-related activities.	3.27	0.53	1.95	0.74
10	The principal timely resolves key issues in organizational, operational, or resource-related activities.	3.59	0.51	1.91	0.63
11	The principal remains consistent in solving key issues in organizational, operational, or resource-related activities.	3.34	0.54	1.92	0.67
12	The principal deals with key issues in an effective manner.	3.63	0.58	1.98	0.74
13	He sets up an accepted procedure to plan short-term and long-term goals.	3.47	0.64	1.68	0.81
14	He ensures effective allocation of resources to achieve such goals.	3.22	0.67	1.71	0.85
15	The principal focuses on maintaining the financial records.	3.16	0.53	1.93	0.61
16	He plans an effective school budget.	3.21	0.51	1.99	0.39
17	He prepares the school budget keeping the mission and vision of the organization in view.	3.44	0.54	1.81	0.69
18	He ensures accountability for all funds.	3.45	0.56	1.92	0.41
19	He ensures following the departmental rules in handling financial issues.	3.49	0.61	1.98	0.54
20	He follows policies to ensure school accountability.	3.33	0.63	1.97	0.81
21	The principal establishes strategies to include all stakeholders in school projects.	3.39	0.52	1.53	0.78
22	He allows them to share in the process of management decisions.	3.54	0.59	1.91	0.71
23	He shares responsibilities with all stakeholders following their skills.	3.81	0.52	1.85	0.77
24	He ensures the smooth functioning of the school with the help of all stakeholders.	3.89	0.45	1.49	0.81

Table 5 clearly indicates that there exists a positive relationship extroversion scores of school principals and their organizational management, as $r=.613$ with the $p=.006$. It further tells that organizational management is dependent on extrovert school leadership. In Table 6, this can be seen that the extrovert school principals have a mean score of 46.33 with $SD=3.06$ whereas introvert principals have a mean score of 29.81 with $SD=3.98$. Furthermore $t=3.19$ for $p=.002$, shows that there exists a significant difference in organizational management of extrovert and introvert school principals.

Table 5. Correlation coefficients for extroversion scores and organizational management

Correlation coefficient	Organizational management
Extroversion scores	$r=.613$ $p=.006$

Table 6. Significant difference between organizational management of extrovert and introvert principals

Performance dimension	Extroversion		Introversion		T	P
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Organizational management	46.33	3.06	29.81	3.98	3.19	.002

4. DISCUSSION

The present study followed a positivist paradigm and adopted a correlational research design. A survey method was deployed for data collection. The demographic information form and the research instruments were sent to the respondents through registered mail. SPSS version 24.0 was deployed for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation was calculated. Pearson correlation r and t -test were deployed using inferential stats.

Based on data analysis, the following are brief findings of this study. Introvert principals did not have had a clear concept of the vision and mission of the organization, they did not understand all compulsory rules and regulations of the organization, and they did not employ all compulsory rules and regulations of the organization in true letter and spirit. These results are in line with past research in a similar area [26]–[28].

Extrovert principals showed maximum interest in holding a clear concept of vision and mission of the organization, presented this vision and mission of the organization to all concerned effectively, effectively dealt with key issues, set up an accepted procedure to plan short-term and long-term goals, shared responsibilities with all stakeholders following their skills, and ensured the smooth functioning of the school with the help of all stakeholders. These results coincided with the results of those [29], [30]. It was explored that a positive relationship exists between organizational management and extrovert school leadership. Moreover, a significant difference in organizational management was also explored between extrovert and introvert school principals. It was deduced that extrovert school leadership better performed in organizational management duties as compared to introvert school principals. These findings confirmed the results of previous studies [31], [32].

5. CONCLUSION

It is concluded that extrovert school leaders perform their duties well. By and large, the extrovert principals follow performance indicators while performing their duties. In comparison, introverted school principals show less interest in the organizational management of their schools. Moreover, school leaders hold a positive correlation between extroversion scores and organizational management. Also, there exists a significant difference in organizational management of extrovert and introvert school principals. It is, therefore, concluded that extrovert school leaders have a greater potential to command and control their institutions than introvert school leaders. It is recommended that the performance indicators and standards of school principals should be effectively communicated to the school leadership. A comprehensive professional development program of school principals is also recommended in this regard. Introvert principals should be provided necessary psychological training to reduce this shortcoming of personality.

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